

D6.2 – Communication and dissemination strategy

WP6 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Replication strategies

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Table of Content

Executive Summary	2
1 Introduction	3
2 H ₂ SHIFT communication and dissemination strategy at M6	3
2.1 Communication	3
2.1.1 Project logo, website and social media accounts	4
2.1.2 Videos	4
2.1.3 Press releases	4
2.1.4 Visual content	5
2.1.5 Technical content	5
2.1.6 Other communication activities	5
2.2 Dissemination	5
2.2.1 Workshops and attendance of events planning	6
2.2.2 Cross fertilisation with other H2020/HEU OITB initiatives	7
3 Next steps	7

Executive Summary

This document outlines the communication and dissemination strategy for project H₂SHIFT and the activities undertaken in the first six months of the project.

The communication and dissemination strategy at M6 overall confirms the draft plan presented in the Part B of H₂SHIFT Grant Agreement. Some initial activities have also taken place, as follows:

- Creation of communication material for the project (see also D6.1): visual identity, templates, first release of the project website; first release of the official project presentation.
- Opening of the social media accounts e.g. on LinkedIn and X.
- Collection of material from partners to support continuous updating of the project communication material.
- Planning of events for the first two years of the projects.

Further versions of this document will provide updates about the results of the communication and dissemination activity undertaken in the period and an update of the strategy itself, particularly for dissemination.

1 Introduction

The H₂SHIFT project aims to establish the first innovation and excellence hub for innovative hydrogen production technologies open to startups and SMEs from Europe and globally. The communication and dissemination strategy supports the awareness raising about the project but also the involvement of a wide range of different stakeholders across the hydrogen value chain. A draft plan for communication and dissemination has been presented within the Grant Agreement; this document, which will be regularly updated, will report on its updating and on the implementation of the strategy.

2 H₂SHIFT communication and dissemination strategy at M6

2.1 Communication

Project communication activities start at the same time as the project itself and are directed to the general public. They aim to raise the awareness of the project. Messages delivered are suitable for non-technical audience also and they include information such as project objectives, timeline, participants, activities, progress and results. Means of communication include the project website, social media posts and general articles.

Communication activities are supported by the creation of a project visual identity or brand (colour palette, font, logo), as implemented in the project website, social media account graphic material (headers, avatars, posts), project publications (templates for deliverables and presentations; general project presentation) and printouts (roll ups and brochures, for examples).

H₂SHIFT communication activities have a number of KPIs defined in the Grant Agreement and reported below. The Table also summarises the activities undertaken so far and the next steps, which are further illustrated in the following sections.

Table 1 H₂SHIFT communication KPIs and targets with activities undertaken by M6 and planned for the M6-M12 period

Communication activities	KPIs	Update M6	Next steps (M6-M12)
Logo Creation: Project identity creation with a clear professional logo	1 Logo	Delivered at M3; brand book delivered at M6	-
OITB Project Website: Project's website with clear references on project's information, services provided, and Open Calls details	More than 50,000 between visits and post hits during project.	Website launched at M6	Create social media posts to illustrate the project and referring to the project website so to increase traffic of users.
Social Media accounts: X and LinkedIn account	1,500 followers.	X and LinkedIn accounts opened at M5	Set up a monthly editorial plan
Video: one video of presentation of the project and the services provided by the OITB	4,500 views on YouTube	YouTube channel graphic material ready at M5	Open YouTube channel and start posting short videos
Press Release: +10 press release by local or specialist or online media	15,000 readership	-	Organise press release e.g. around the next project events: GA meeting in Autumn 2024; launch

Communication activities	KPIs	Update M6	Next steps (M6-M12)
			of SEP; participation to large sectorial events
Visual content: flyers, brochures, posters, info-graphics, roll-ups that will be used in online and offline events to present project contents	More than 1,500 unit of materials produced	Communication material prepared including a first version of the official project presentation and some graphic material for the website	Creation of first version of project flyers/brochures and roll ups
Technical content: elaboration of technical articles and booklets within specialist magazines, technology websites and any other relevant media	At least 8 publications	-	Support to partners for the delivery of at least one technical article on project progress during first year of project

2.1.1 Project logo, website and social media accounts

Deliverable D6.1 contains information on the communication material prepared for the project up to M6, including the logo. Different versions of the logo can be found in the Brand book in Annex 1 of D6.1.

The project website is live since the end of August 2024 and its first release is described within D6.1. Its launch represents a cornerstone of the communication activity and it enables the start of a comprehensive awareness raising activity.

While the social media accounts on LinkedIn and X have been open since M5, posting has been delayed so to organise an information campaign with the following main objectives:

- Providing snippets of information about the project while referring back to the project website for more comprehensive details;
- Presenting the partners and their contribution to the projects;
- Presenting the test lines;
- Anticipating and following the main events of the project: general assemblies, launch of the SEP, start of showcases, opening of the calls etc.

An editorial plan is to be prepared aiming to plan up to a month of posting with regular features (up to 2 posts per week, publicised across /cross referenced between LinkedIn, X, YouTube and the appropriate section of the website as suitable).

2.1.2 Videos

Video materials prepared for the project will be uploaded onto the project YouTube channel and opportunely publicised. Short video materials might include short reports of the project events, partners interviews, overview of the test lines. Partners will be invited to contribute and/or support will be provided by ENVI and CDI. Meetings such as the General Assemblies will be used to collect material. A video presentation of the project will be prepared within M18.

2.1.3 Press releases

Press releases are to be prepared, with the support of Fondazione Polimi, specifically for significant project events, for instance: the launch of the SEP, the launch of the showcases and the Open Calls. Further potential opportunities will be explored with the project partners with the aim to propose a first plan with M18.

2.1.4 Visual content

With the definition of the project website and the first official presentation, further visual material will be prepared. A project roll-up and a first version of a flyer will be produced to support, advertising of the project during some 2024 Autumn events, e.g. the Hydrogen Week. The visual material prepared will be exploited also for other communication activities such as social media posts and updating of the website.

2.1.5 Technical content

Technical articles could be produced for instance to:

- Describe the project (target release: M9)
- Describe the progress after the first year of the project, e.g.: describe the SEP, the advancement of the test lines etc (target release: M12)
- Illustrate the capabilities of the project, e.g. the test lines, the showcases, the results of the open calls (from the second year of the project).

Press releases and technical articles will be coordinated so to keep a good level of attention on the project.

2.1.6 Other communication activities

One half-page article, publicising Envipark and Politecnico di Torino facilities and mentioning their participation in H₂SHIFT, has been prepared in M6 to appear on a special hydrogen issue of Italian newspaper Il Sole 24 Ore to be published in M7.

2.2 Dissemination

Project dissemination builds up on the communication activity and aims to engage the stakeholders of project H₂SHIFT to support the expected impact of the project and the exploitation of its results. H₂SHIFT Ecosystem of stakeholders includes the network of consortium members, potential customers, and end-users, that will be involved thanks to the services offered by the OITB and project actions implemented. H₂SHIFT consortium already represent a strong base of academia, technological centres, and actors coming from different industrial sectors, with a very large networks covering the whole value chain.

WP6 will work in synergy with WP2, which will produce by M9 a map of the H₂SHIFT ecosystem, collecting data and characteristics of reachable stakeholder and their needs, strategy, action plan and tools for their engagement (deliverable D2.2 Ecosystem Map). Also, information gathered by WP3 in terms of profiling of test line users and their needs (deliverable D3.2 Individuation of the target groups, and analysis of the profile of their needs towards innovation, due M7) will be exploited. These evaluations will integrate and detail the first assessment of the H₂SHIFT stakeholders and dissemination activities targeted to them, as shown below.

Table 2 H₂SHIFT initial categorisation of stakeholders

Stakeholder category	Objective	Dissemination activities
Startups and SMEs	Accelerate and improve knowledge and technical sharing	Workshops, communication activities in general, training
OITB	Improve the efficiency of H ₂ SHIFT OITB through knowledge sharing	Workshop, fairs, conferences, and public events
Technology providers	Interaction with hydrogen related technology providers for new applications and partnerships	Fairs, exhibitions, public events, technical workshops

Stakeholder category	Objective	Dissemination activities
Science community	Knowledge transferability and inputs for R&D activities	Scientific publications, conferences, workshops
Policy makers and governments	Awareness on potential benefits	H ₂ SHIFT achievements, policy recommendations

Dissemination activities initially planned by the project, with relevant KPIs, are described below. These activities and KPIs will also be updated with the information collated and elaborated within WP2 and WP3. The table also provide some initial activities undertaken within the first 6 months of the project; such activities are briefly described in the following subsections.

Table 3 H₂SHIFT dissemination KPIs and targets with activities undertaken and planned for M6-M12

Dissemination activities	KPIs	Update M6	Next steps (M6-M12)
Technical workshops: dedicated thematic workshop involving target groups of relevant stakeholders. Within the workshops communication among end-users and technical actors will be ensured. Moreover, communication activities with others OITB will be held to share knowledge and best practices. The workshops will be organised with different scopes: 1) present the OITB and engage potential users and provide information on services foreseen. 2) technology and services providers will be involved for workshops on knowledge sharing. 3) OITB knowledge sharing with already existing OITB and 4) for sharing solutions and lessons learned from the testbeds.	At least 2 workshops with a total number of participants equal to 80	WP6 produced a calendar of relevant industry events throughout Europe that could be exploited for organising the workshops and that could be attended to engage with relevant stakeholders and to disseminate H ₂ SHIFT project results.	Start planning the timeline of the workshops to ensure appropriate measures can be taken to e.g. book venues and spaces within large conferences.
Fairs and exhibitions: participation in various conferences, exhibitions, fairs and commercial events	At least 15 events attended		Scope out events to be exploited for year 2 to 4 of the project
H2020/HEU OITB initiatives: cross-fertilizations and synergies with other OITBs will be fostered thanks to strict cooperation with already existing OITB.	At least 3 joint meeting/activity	-	List and get in touch with OITB projects

2.2.1 Workshops and attendance of events planning

ENVI, together with CDI and Fondazione Politecnico di Milano, i.e., the WP2 and WP5 leaders, has built a time map of industry events for the duration of the project, to be further filled with the contribution of other partners throughout the project timeline. The events identified so far are the major European events that repeat regularly and that attract H₂SHIFT potential stakeholders.

In the first year of the project, from October 2024, a few events have been identified to be scoped out for future hosting of the project's engagement activities, i.e., workshops. Amongst them are events of national, European and global relevance such as The business booster of EIT InnoEnergy, the Hydrogen Week, Hyvolution. The plan is for partners to exploit their 2024 participation on behalf of other projects to assess relevance for project H₂SHIFT and to identify opportunities for proposing H₂SHIFT workshops in the next years' editions.

The calendar is cross referenced to the project timeline so that timing of expected delivery of project results can be referred to for workshop or other dissemination activities as matched with a significant event. For instance, Hyvolution 2025 (end of January) has been identified as a potential opportunity for presenting the catalogue of H₂SHIFT service offering.

This cross linking will be continued throughout the next months also ensuring other activities planned within other WPs are mapped to exploit synergies and maximise impact of dissemination.

2.2.2 Cross fertilisation with other H2020/HEU OITB initiatives

This activity will require gathering of information about other OITBs, which started in M4. Contacts will be made to exploit opportunities for synergies; furthermore, specialist events dedicated to OITB will be scoped out. Initiatives such as the OITB village at IndTech 2022 will be monitored.

3 Next steps

The next steps in the implementation of the communication and dissemination activity have been described above, with the next version of this deliverable reporting on the achievements. Furthermore, while the communication strategy is sufficiently planned out, the dissemination strategy is likely to require some updating with the results of the activities of WP2 and WP3. Finally, as the first results of the project mature, the implementation of such strategy will also take place.